

SCIENTIFIC BASIS OF CROP CROPPING.

Isayeva Kamola Davronovna¹

Khaidarova Iroda Irgashovna²

To'rayeva Dilafruz Ikhtiyorovna³

4th year students of

¹⁻²⁻³Termiz Institute of Agricultural Technologies and Innovative Development.

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The purpose of the research: The scientific basis of alternating sowing of crops by fields and years is called crop rotation. Such alternating planting creates conditions for controlling the amount of organic matter in the soil, effective control of weeds, plant diseases and pests, provides the granular structure of the soil, improves the nutrition and water regime, and improves the effectiveness of the applied fertilizers. increases and prevents soil erosion.

Content of the study: Different plants accumulate organic residues in different amounts in the soil. Perennial grasses and winter cereals produce large amounts of organic residue, spring cereals produce less, and inter-row crops produce very little organic residue. For example, 3-year-old alfalfa accumulates 10-11 t of manure and 300-500 kg of biological nitrogen per hectare.

If a crop is not planted in the same field for more than 3 years, it is a repeated crop, if it is planted during the rotation period or more, it is a perennial crop, and the long-term planting of the same crop in the same field is called monolattura. Planting of crops at an optimal level in turn forms a system of crop rotation, which is based on the developed structure of cultivated areas. Each crop rotation has a certain area on the farm, and the area is divided into several fields of approximately equal area. For example, if corn, winter wheat, beets, barley, and oats are to be planted in the crop rotation, the area is divided into 5 fields and one of these crops is grown in each of them. Under these conditions, it takes 5 years for the rotation of crops in the fields, that is, the rotation period lasts for so many years. Rotation is the time taken to plant each field according to the scheme determined by the crop rotation. In the example above, a specific crop will start replanting every field after 5 years. In this case, the rotation period is equal to the number of fields.

The list of crop groups included in the rotation, the order of their rotation or the ratio of the fields occupied by the crops in the rotation is called the rotation scheme.

In crop rotation, the crop grown before each crop is its predecessor. For example, if corn is followed by winter wheat, the former is the predecessor crop to the latter. Winter cereals are good predecessors for most crops. These crops,

which leave a large amount of plant residues in the field, are harvested early and the soil is cultivated in a timely manner. Legumes enrich the soil with nitrogen and improve its physical properties. It is a good predecessor for grain crops, potatoes, beets and other crops because it breaks down difficult-to-assimilate phosphorus compounds to easily-assimilable levels. can be a good predecessor for A clean plow is considered a separate predecessor. Sowing fall grain crops on such lands, which are not busy with field crops, but are cultivated throughout the season, gives good results. A disease or pest that is harmful to some crops may not pose a threat to others. For example, the caterpillar causes significant damage to sunflower, tobacco, alfalfa and hemp. can not have a harmful effect on corn and sorghum. Bedsa corn, sorghum and grain crops are not affected by cotton wilt and ensure the reduction of wilt pathogens in the soil. Therefore, they are planted as a predecessor crop for cotton.

In order to use arable land throughout the year, to strengthen the fodder base, to increase soil fertility, to reduce diseases and pests of main crops, intermediate and siderate crops are grown. Crops grown in addition to the main crops are called alternate and intermediate crops. They are planted when the field is not busy with the main crops. Repetitive crops are planted in the second half of the summer after the main predecessor crop has been harvested in the forage field of the rotation and harvested in the fall. Catch crops are planted between the rows after the main crop is harvested in the fall or while they are growing, and the overwintered crop is harvested for livestock in the spring. Crops that are not intended to be harvested and are planted with the purpose of adding to the soil and driving them are called siderate crops (green manures).

The following three types of rotation are distinguished: field rotation, fodder rotation and special rotation. They, in turn. Crop rotation is divided into several types depending on the direction of cultivation, the main commodity product, the number of fields, the rotation period and other indicators. Field rotation is intended for the cultivation of technical (cotton, hemp, flax) and grain crops, as well as fodder, and fodder rotation is intended for the cultivation of coarse and succulent fodder. A crop rotation that is organized around a livestock farm or farm and is intended for the production of succulents and green fodder is called preform rotation. The rotation of perennial and annual grasses for making hay and feeding cattle is called hay-pasture rotation.

Crops that require special agrotechnics and conditions (police, vegetables, tobacco, etc.) are grown in special crop rotation fields. In soils prone to decay, crop rotations are organized to protect them, field crops, fodder crops and

special crop rotations are grown. In saline lands, special reclamation field rotation is used.

In such rotations, in order to meet the demand of livestock for fodder, the majority of the area of nutritious crops is allocated to perennial grasses, silage crops, and ornamental fruits. Organic manure collected in livestock farms is widely used for fertilizing crops.

